

CRAFTS AND THE SOUVENIR BUSINESS: TESTIMONY FROM A TOURISTIC CITY IN NORTHEASTERN BRAZIL

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ABSTRACT

The paper provides descriptive testimonial on artifacts found in three important craft fairs at Natal, a touristic city in northeastern Brazil. Based on an exploratory observation at the chosen commercial points, the present study documents the status of the souvenirs business in the region as it faces touristic development. The study aims to discuss the role of crafts in the souvenir trade, particularly in the context of the very few formally educated designers at the market. A wide range of techniques, materials and utilities were observed. Symbolic aspects, such as the regional stereotypes and different levels of commitment to vernacular languages, as well as know-how prompted special interest during the observation. It was thus brought to our attention that marketing and legacy preservation should be conciliated if a culturally sustainable business is desired by producers, merchants, visitors and natives.

Keywords: Design; Crafts; Souvenir.

INTRODUCTION: A CITY AND ITS TOURISM

Brazil, a country with almost eight thousand kilometers of shore, has a very favorable position for touristic progress, as is currently happening. The country is divided into five geographical regions: North, Northeast, Central-West, Southeast and South. With the exception of the Central-West, all of these regions have their own coast, and consequently, beach-centered touristic potential, especially due to the climate of the country. Being near the Equator, the Northeast region is well known for its almost perennial warm weather. This region also boasts a rich cultural tradition. Therefore, tourism in this region has a very strong

prospective - and design is likely to both support and be supported by this economic feature.

One of the many aspects of the tourism industry that the study and practice of design can influence is the souvenir and crafts business. This paper focuses on this discussion, mainly by documenting the product collections in tourism-centered craft fairs at a developing northeastern Brazilian city.

Natal is the capital of the Rio Grande do Norte State (Figure 01), a municipality of approximately 800,000 citizens (IBGE, 2010). It was founded in 1599 along the Atlantic shore, and its Old Town was classified as an area to be preserved by Brazil’s National Institute of Historical and Artistic Heritage (Instituto do Patrimônio Histórico e Artístico Nacional - IPHAN) in 2010. The climate consists of warm temperatures all year long (in 2009, minimum of 20 °C and maximum of 32.2 °C) (Alves et al 2009), with occasional rain episodes. Another significant characteristic of Natal is a substantial contrast between richness and poverty, as well as some other serious social and infra-structural problems. These problems, however, do not seem to strongly affect the growth of touristic activity.

Since the 1980s, the state of Rio Grande do Norte has been rising as a major tourism destination. The coastal cities, especially Natal, are the most famous tourism spots. In addition, the capital was elected to be one of the host cities for the 2014 FIFA World Cup, so it is expected that tourism will increase over the next few years as a result of the high visibility of this event.

As expected for a shore side location, the tourism of Natal and its metropolitan region is mainly based on attractions that come from the sea and beaches: rides by boat, diving, kite-surfing, sand-boarding and seafood restaurants, as well as resort facilities such as aquatic parks and spas.

Figure 01: A map of Brazil with Natal, Rio Grande do Norte and the Northeast Region highlighted. Cartographic base: Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística (2011) (modified by the authors).

According to data released by the State Tourism Secretary for the local press (Nominuto, 2010), the number of visitors to Rio Grande do Norte grew 12.43% in 2010. It is estimated that 2.6 million people went to the state, 93% of them from other parts of Brazil and 7% from other countries. Based on this information, Natal is currently a “domestic” tourist destination.

Concerning tourism, crafts are very important for Natal’s image and the associated businesses are strongly linked to the local culture. The city also has many craft stores besides the independent sellers. According to Souza (1991), at least since the 1960’s craftspeople from the state of Rio Grande do Norte use their abilities as a source of financial complement to their income in offseason; it is also very common that they organize themselves in cooperatives until this date.

The importance of this activity for Natal can be measured by FIART (Feira Internacional de Artesanato), an international crafts exhibition that has happened at the city every year since 1996. In 2010, this event was held at Natal’s largest convention center, and according to the local media (Nominuto, 2010), lasted 10 days, was visited by 70,000 people and moved approximately R\$5 million

through the local economy (nearly €2 million at the time).

It is also important to note that, although the crafts industry is a very fertile field for design activity, the state of Rio Grande do Norte has little tradition in formal design education. It was not until 2009 that higher education design courses were created, one in Graphic Design at a private university and another on Design at a public university, both in the capital. Thus, there are few formally educated professionals of design in the area.

SOUVENIRS AND CRAFTS

The present study sought to report on the current situation of the products sold in craft fairs in Natal, documenting the status of one of the area’s few design-centered economical activities. It also aimed to reflect on the region’s souvenir business, and the role of crafts and design in this kind of trade because it tends to grow along with the expansion of the tourism industry.

It is a well-known fact that souvenirs are amongst the many products of consumption that tourists are interested in while visiting any city in the world. They are often considered kitsch, but key chains, T-shirts, magnets and bibelots portraying the sights of the visited city are commonly purchased by tourists. Gordon (1986, p.135) notices that “the universality of the souvenir can be understood in the light of its underlying role or function. As an actual object, it concretizes or makes tangible what was otherwise only an intangible state”.

The Northeast of Brazil, in general, is associated with picturesque, bucolic landscapes and modest people; it is strongly portrayed by the national media for its natural sights, popular traditions and legacies. Thus, as a northeastern city, local crafts made by traditional techniques form the bulk of exotic souvenirs to be bought in Natal.

The definition of craft used here is based on a study published by SEBRAE (Serviço Brasileiro de Apoio às Micro e Pequenas Empresas, 2004), the Brazilian service for the support of micro and small businesses. It divides crafts into nine categories: (i) Popular Art; (ii) Crafts; (iii) Handmade Crafts; (iv) Typical Alimentary Products; (v) Semi-industrial and Industrial Products; (vi) Indigenous Products; (vii)

Traditional Crafts; (viii) Cultural Referenced Crafts; and (ix) Conceptual Crafts.

Because the study has a free testimonial nature, the method used was equally informal and exploratory as well as based on an empirical observation of the products sold at three major craft fairs in Natal's metropolitan region during January of 2011.

The first place visited was the "Shopping do Artesanato Potiguar" (Rio Grande de Norte's Crafts Mall) (Figure 02) on January 11th, 2011. The place consisted of a four-floor building, formerly a hotel, filled with 180 different commercial spots (divided across stores, stands, and some restaurants and bars), several dedicated to selling local crafts. It is located in the Ponta Negra district, one of the locales most visited by tourists.

The second point visited was the "Centro de Turismo" (Tourism Center) (Figure 03) on January 12th, 2011. According to its administration, it is a building dated from the late 19th Century that used to be a residence, then later turned into a homeless hostel, then an orphanage, and then a prison. In 1976, it was transformed by the government into a center for tourism support with an information bureau, a restaurant, a night club, a gallery, and 38 craft stores. It is located next to Praia do Meio and Natal's Old Town Center.

The third and last place observed was the crafts fair in Cajueiro de Pirangi (Pirangi Beach's Cashew Tree) on January 13th, 2011 (Figure 04). The beach is located at Parnamirim, part of Natal's metropolitan region. The fair is right next to one of the most famous local attractions, the World's Biggest Cajueiro (Cashew Tree). It has 27 working craft stands.

In general, the crafts sold at the three different fairs were very similar. Therefore, it was possible to assume that the production of crafts seen at the three separate locations could easily be considered as a single group with very similar patterns.

Natal's regional souvenir and craft fairs are filled with all kinds of products, the majority of which fit in the categories of SEBRAE, including even semi-industrial and industrial products. Thus, the concept of crafts used here tended to be broad, related to more than just vernacular handmade artifacts based exclusively on traditional techniques, materials and artistic themes.

Figure 02: Shopping do Artesanato Potiguar (2011).

Figure 03: Centro de Turismo (2011).

Figure 04: Pirangi Beach's crafts fair (2011).

EXAMPLES OF CORRELATED STUDIES

Design and Crafts is a theme that has been deeply discussed in specialized literature, even on an historical context. The approaches contemplate many topics, as the role of crafts in the framework of industrialized societies or the potential of adding

value to products created by traditional communities through design consultancy.

About the specific relations among crafts, souvenirs and cultural aspects (such as regional identity), they have also been studied by many authors. To mention some Brazilian examples, Molin and Schaefer (2009) associate the concept of kitsch to craft souvenirs, including a deliberation about popular culture and consumer behavior; Oliveira (2008) critically observed how a touristic-centered crafts mall in the state of Bahia built its communication with the clientele; Machado and Siqueira (2008) discuss the souvenir industry as a symbolic feature of many social aspects, using Petropolis, a historical and touristic city in the state of Rio de Janeiro, as an example. These last authors also observed that the purchase of souvenirs may have a variety of motivations. Pinho (2002) also approaches the matter in the book chapter “Produtos artesanais e o mercado turístico” (Crafts and the touristic market). Another example which discusses the relations among crafts, culture and trade is the paper by Barbosa (2005), focusing on the identity issues of a certain community in the state of Minas Gerais through an analysis of the production observed at a local crafts fair.

Barroso Neto (1999) is a Brazilian design critic that addresses the topic. His study approaches many issues and concepts involving Brazilian crafts, such as identity, culture and relations with design consultancy - to mention a few. The author presents a critical vision concerning the large scale production of crafts to be sold as souvenirs, especially those which vulgarize and stereotype cultures.

An American paper that should be mentioned is “What makes a craft souvenir authentic?” (Littrel, Anderson and Brown, 1993). As the title states, the authors discuss the concept of craft souvenirs authenticity, especially through a survey among consumers.

This matter had also been investigated through surveys by a New Zealander paper (Asplet and Cooper, 2000), specifically about textiles and clothing items.

Wilkins (2010) reported a research conducted in Australia, which mainly analyzed the motivations of souvenir purchase, considering many variables, including the user’s gender. Another work to be cited

is the book “Souvenirs: the material culture of tourism” (Hitchcock, Teague, 2000), which brings many case studies taken on different parts of the world.

One of the few studies found in design-centered publications was the article “Craft, Souvenirs and the Commodification of National Identity in 1970s’ Scotland” by Andrea Peach (2007). At the conclusion of this text, the author observes that the strong historical background of Scotland promoted a sense of “myth”, which permeated its souvenir industry in the 1970’s, maybe inhibiting the emergence of contemporary expressiveness in craft design at the time.

In this brief bibliographical research, it was observed that generally the conflicts between regional authenticity and marketing motivations constitute a concern presented by many studies about craft and souvenirs. This facet shows a very complex condition connecting design and heritage.

SOUVENIRS AND LOCAL IDENTITY: DIRECT REFERENCES

The observed souvenirs frequently convey the local culture, specifically Natal and the nearby cities, as well as the Northeast Region and Brazil itself. This kind of reference probably reveals the diversity of tourists that form the crafts fairs’ clientele.

Among the souvenirs sold, some of them make direct and figurative allusions to the coastal area where Natal is located. The variations in this theme are also broad (including tropical stereotypes, such as palm trees and coconuts). The bottles portraying bucolic beach landscapes made with colored sand (Figure 05) are well-established, iconic pieces of craft sold in Natal, as well as in many other cities on the northeastern coast. However, one of the most effective icons for Natal is the caju (cashew) because the Cajueiro de Pirangi (Pirangi Cashew Tree) makes this fruit a symbol of the city and widely shown by the national media. In the example of the cashew-shaped piggybank sold at Pirangi fair (Figure 06), the fruit form, however, did not seem enough to symbolize the city, so a dolphin, one of the most searched for animals by tourists, and the saying “Natal-RN” were painted onto the product. The Sun is also a very common symbol for Natal.

Natal has been advertised as “The City of the Sun” or “The Sun’s Bride” for a long time. A rubber keychain shaped as the Sun with the city’s name inscribed therefore might be considered a souvenir based on the local identity (Figure 07).

Figure 05: Colored sand bottles (2011).

Figure 06: Cashew-themed souvenirs: piggybank (2011).

Figure 07: Sun-shaped rubber keychain (2011).

The Northeast region of Brazil is considered by many people a land of homogeneous culture.

Consequently, the term “The Northeast” constantly replaces the names of the cities in this region, including Natal. With this mindset, many merchants sell items referring to the northeastern culture at the observed fairs as well.

One of the most significant aspects of the northeastern references is the tradition of the historical countryside. The aesthetic aspects of the sertanejos (hinterlander) and the cangaceiros (hinterland bandits) can be clearly seen in the product’s designs. The sertanejo is the inhabitant of the sertão (remote interior): an area far away from the coast with a semi-arid climate with unique cultural aspects. The sertão of the northeastern states of Brazil is simultaneously associated with poverty and preserved traditions. The cangaceiros, in turn, are very important figures for the northeastern sertão history; they formed armed clandestine gangs in the late 19th to the first half of the 20th century, performing robbery, murders and invasions. However, the cangaceiros had a very singular look: their distinctive outfits turned their figure strongly iconic all over Brazil. Through the decades, their image then came to be associated with the Northeast. Therefore, the world of the sertanejo (including their art, clothing designs and the sertão’s landscape), as well as the cangaceiros’ figures, is widely exploited as inspirational elements for many kinds of products, including handcrafted pieces. These objects probably have a special appeal for Brazilian visitors from other regions searching for exotic northeastern souvenirs.

The semi-circular, richly adorned leather hats are normally associated to cangaceiros, while a simpler version of the leather hats and garments are linked to the general sertanejo (Figure 08). These pieces have been out of fashion for a long time (although some people, especially in rural areas, still use the simpler design for hats), but the strong meaning they have in representing the Northeast make them a valuable, authentic item. Other objects in leather, such as sandals in traditional designs, which are potentially more wearable, but equally iconic, are also sold (Figure 09).

Handmade clay statuettes, with a very singular, easily recognizable design, also commonly portray

the people from the sertão in their daily activities. This portrayal could be either a cangaceiro, a group of people performing local music (Figure 10), or a hard-working woman, to mention a few examples. The combination of the aesthetic language, the techniques used to produce them and the very figure of the sertanejo also put these pieces among the most authentically northeastern items that can be sold, even though similar objects can also be found in other Brazilian states, such as Minas Gerais.

Figure 08: Traditional leather hats: “cangaceiro-styled” and simple style (2011).

Figure 09: Leather sandal-shaped key chains (2011).

Besides the products made with traditional craft techniques, there are also products that convey the northeastern feeling through more contemporary mediums. The regional woodcut graphic design, for example, is often associated with the Northeast by the media as well. The language also conveys an instantaneous “northeastern” touch to any graphic composition. This kind of reference can be observed as an illustration printed on a synthetic fabric

handbag (Figure 11); the motifs are familiar to the vernacular artwork as well. Still concerning contemporary designs, there is also the case of a silk-screened T-shirt with the typical northeastern interjection “ôxente!” (“oh people!”, said to express surprise in both good and bad contexts) written over a contemporary “Smiley” figure that happens to be wearing a cangaceiro hat (Figure 12).

Figure 10: Clay statuettes portraying sertanejos (2011).

Figure 11: Handbag with a regional cutwood-styled print (2011).

The local identity in the products might also refer not only to Natal and the Northeast region but also to Brazil itself. Items portraying the Brazilian flag and colors are common, as the example of the ceramic mug in Figure 13 illustrates. Brazilian soccer teams from Rio de Janeiro and São Paulo are also pretty common themes. The image of Amazonian Brazil, which is famous all over the world, is also exploited, even though the Amazonian Forest is a considerable distance from Natal, both geographically and culturally. Specifically, you might see statues of rainforest birds, as well as T-shirts

with their image. Other common items are the Havaianas® flip-flops, a contemporary classic of Brazilian industrial design (sometimes adorned with beads added by the craftspeople).

Figure 12: A t-shirt with a smiley dressed as a sertanejo (2011).

Figure 13: Mugs with Brazil's flag (2011).

Another kind of product sold at the observed fairs is the one with foreign identities. It might seem eccentric, but at those fairs themed to tourists in search of legitimate local mementos, there are also products evoking images from external backgrounds. Indian-themed clothing (referred to by locals as “hippie-style”) is quite common, especially their designs and prints. The statuettes portraying stereotypical African feminine figures are also very common, and they might be the closest ones to the local culture, considering the strong influence of Africans in the contemporary Brazilian population. A Jamaica-inspired t-shirt with the saying “Natal-RN” was also spotted, but the pieces that proved to be the most exotic were cartoon themed statuettes found at Pirangi’s fair because they seemed to

represent a simultaneous negation of both tradition and regionalism; this kind of product is also mentioned in a paper by Silva (2007).

In fact, many pieces apparently do not communicate any regional identity at all. Dolls and bibelots of ballerinas, fairy-tale farm girls and cute animals, towels with floral motifs, humorous T-shirts without local references, gift-mugs with sayings such as “Mom”, leopard print purses, erotica, flower vases, and other products all fall in this category. Surprisingly, one can find them side-by-side with very vernacular-based items.

NEARBY KNOW-HOW

The local know-how in crafts places emphasis on textiles as important products for expression. The main divisions seem to be rough cotton products, lace and raw vegetable fibers. It is safe to say that the strong cotton culture in the state of Rio Grande do Norte over the 19th and 20th centuries provided propitious conditions for the development of these first types of products. In fact, textile techniques now fill the handicraft and souvenirs fairs with very usable/wearable products that at the same time have a local identity.

The cotton goods form a much searched for group of products not only for tourists but also for natives. This fact says a lot about their quality and meaning for local consumers and producers. It is important to notice that “local” refers to the whole region because the products might now even come from nearby cities or states. Among the rough cotton products, house wares seem to be the most prominent: hammocks, rugs, curtains, kitchen clothing, and table towels (Figure 14) are all available. They are generally offered in a large variety of colors and the mesh structures are generally formed by abstract, geometrical patterns (the texture is similar to tweed). The cotton strings are also used to make adornments, knotted or artistically sewn.

Lace products are also very important, not only commercially but culturally as well. As happens in many parts of the world, the figure of the lace craftsperson, generally a woman that has mastered the technique, is very prominent - called “rendeira” in Brazil. The complex practice results in products that, although common in many countries, are

usually associated with the northeastern culture by the Brazilian media. These lace products are very diverse. Clothes, table sets and towels are all common, but some more curious products, such as toilet paper holders (Figure 15), might also be found around the fairs.

Figure 14: Cotton hammocks (2011).

Figure 15: Lace toilet paper holders (2011).

Raw vegetable fibers are also frequently employed materials in handcraft. They are crafted like textiles strings, even emulating lace patterns, and are mainly used in table clothing and fashion accessories, such as hats, purses and hand wallets (Figure 16). Edible goods are also very common crafts. They represent much of the native flora and are among

the local population's favorite products as well. The toasted cashew nut, which might be caramelized, not only represents the symbolic fruit of the region but also is an omnipresent produce at craft fairs. Bottles of "cachaça" (distilled beverage from sugar cane) from local producers are also widely commercialized. Pepper bottles, cashew pulp sweets and handmade biscuits were found during our study as well (Figure 17).

In the case of the products mentioned in this section, the identity is not conveyed directly or figuratively but subtly represented as the consequence of natural resources, economic aspects and habits of the population. Such aspects are clearly not artificially divided at the political boundaries, so they will also be very common in other parts of Brazil.

About this topic, the division of SEBRAE from the state of Rio Grande do Norte (2003) affirms that "our crafts are not exclusively the result of the naivety of illiterate people that, touched by an inexplicable force, ably work with raw materials. It's an art matured in tradition" (p.12, translated). The institution also affirms that the local crafts "flourishes from the earth" (p.09, translated) and the artisans "domesticate the raw materials roughness" (p.09, translated). Still according to SEBRAE (2003), Rio Grande do Norte's crafts are influenced by Portuguese, Native Brazilian and African cultures, which are largely considered the three bases of the Brazilian people.

Figure 16: Detail of pattern in a vegetable fiber product (2011).

Figure 17: Edible goods at a fair (2011).

NORTHEASTERN IDENTITY

Cultural identity and the notion of genuineness have a significant role in studies regarding crafts and souvenirs, as previously discussed. Natal is located seaside and thus, images connected to this kind of environment are obviously used in the local production of such items. Baracuhy (2008) analyzes the images of the Brazilian Northeast's coast as promoted by the media and stated that they generally convey excellent quality of life and paradisiacal places: "This is how the media re-signifies the northeastern space, setting an identity for the Northeast as 'a land without problems', an 'ideal' place for resting and leisure" (Baracuhy, 2008, translated). However, there are contradictions concerning the genuineness of these images. Veloso & Elali (2006) published the study "Quality of life in Natal: myths and realities" ("Qualidade de vida em Natal: mitos e realidades", in Portuguese), where they attest by bibliographical research and surveys that many aspects of the city promoted by the media as very positive, especially concerning quality of life and environment, are actually overestimated and do not accurately correspond to the local inhabitants' perception. The authors' hypothesis, which happens to be confirmed, is that "the supposed high Quality of Life in the city holds a lot more myths than realities" (Veloso & Elali, 2006, p.29, translated). Nevertheless, it has been noticed that many souvenirs sold at the visited craft fairs are based on these idealized images of the city.

The sertão is also portrayed in the souvenirs sold in Natal, as exemplified earlier. Baracuhy (2010) has a hypothesis that the construction of the sertão's

identity is based on stereotypes, noticing that the media uses the *cangaceiro* as a general representation of the northeastern people: "the leather hat, the knife and the cactus became 'memory traces' of these times of violence at the northeastern sertão" (Baracuhy, 2010, p.73, translated). Mello (2010) agrees that the images associated to *cangaceiros* and their artifacts work as representations of Brazil's Northeast. The critic believes that the *cangaceiro*'s semi-circular hat became its main symbol: "no other brand is engraved deeper in the region's collective unconscious [...]. Its closest rival, the raft, falls into the partiality of the coastal appeal, or some particular state or region, for a historical or touristic reason" (Mello, 2010, p.194, translated). On the other hand, Baracuhy (2010) states that the typical problems of the sertão, such as hunger and misery, tend to be omitted in the advertising discourse; it was also observed in the products at the visited fairs.

However, some critics question the association of the northeastern sertão exclusively with traditions. Ferreira & Oliveira (2011), for instance, affirm that the *sertanejo* is often stereotyped, even by the most educated groups, as someone frozen in time and ignorant about technological advances. Despite such criticism, it is evident that the artifacts of the observed fairs made through traditional techniques are probably among the most searched by tourists, perhaps for being regarded as representatives of the local culture; according to Santos (2010), "the city marketing strategy linked to culture is recent in Natal, and apparently it has not yet made a great impact neither in the perception of the tourists, nor of the citizens'" (p.101, translated). If culture were an aspect to be strongly supported in future touristic strategies for Natal, certainly crafts would become even more vital for the city's economy.

DISCUSSIONS AND CONSIDERATIONS

The examples given may just be a small fraction of all the products sold at Natal's region craft fairs. However, it is possible to notice through them the great variety in materials, techniques and themes that compose those stands full of decorative and utilitarian items. Diversity of design while remaining (or not) committed to tradition was the most noticeable aspect. It is therefore important to

emphasize that this case study is not a definitive diagnosis, but an investigation that can yet be expanded or used for future documentations and reflections.

Crafts made through very complex handiwork, such as impressively large lace towels, distinctive natural fiber accessories with elaborated designs and embellishments, vernacular wooden and clay statuettes, sit next to semi-industrialized goods that might also have high artistic, symbolic and economical values, but are in a different craft category. This kind of separation might be considered technologically and culturally biased for some, but might be important for others. The “handmade” and “homemade” products, after all, still have their aggregated value.

“Regionalist-centered” designs are very significant at fairs. They are divided between figurative northeastern icons and typical products derived from the local know-how and natural resources. They both convey the message, and both serve as keepsakes and/or gifts for different reasons to many different people. These pieces, like the others, are sold mainly due to the high tourism activity in this region. This situation seems to create the contradiction between “genuine” and “stereotype”, probably moved by marketing motivations. A hypothesis provided here is that it might put craftspeople in a position of pandering to a client’s preconception and setting aside their own aims and knowledge, as Souza (1991) once observed.

Aside from any supposed conceptual crisis, the crafts and souvenir business is a very promising opportunity for small producers and sellers in a touristic city because visitors are frequent during Natal’s permanent summer. The metropolitan region also offers a good infrastructure for sales, with big craft malls and galleries. Furthermore, as an activity with a great potential to generate income, it is important that the producers are organized and the production professional. They already commonly count on cooperatives, which permit them to sell their goods in major sales spots. But in the long term, the industrial designer might be an important agent to offer help in all phases of creation and production, including the planning of the product’s life cycle. In Brazil, this specific market can be considered a rising opportunity for designers. The emergence of

design in the country occurred in close relation to industrial production, and its association with crafts is not as usual as in other cultures. This recent phenomenon demands further research and practice. A great challenge for industrial designers, and even for the schools of industrial design, is to prepare professionals able to distinguish their roles within the region’s craft, and industrial and touristic settings. When one is working in the field of artistic traditions, sometimes performed exclusively by self-taught artisans, the situation is delicate from both the anthropological and social points of view. The industrial designer must therefore use their professional ability to know what design aspects can be changed while still protecting heritage, when facing consulting situations. Discussing exactly this matter, Lima (2005) states that the cultural value of traditional crafts is simultaneously an advantage and a disadvantage, as it demands “an extreme sensitivity” (translated) to deal with the craftspeople’s values and knowledge.

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